

Practice Guidelines for Labor Epidural Administration

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Background

- A comfortable labor experience is the driving force for patient satisfaction in obstetrics.
- Continuous lumbar epidural (CLE) is the most widely used form of analgesia for laboring women; CLE rates approach 70%.

Problem

- Failure rates of CLE are as high as 24%.
- Failures result in inadequate analgesia, a poor labor experience, and decreased patient satisfaction. They can pose a life-threatening risk when surgery is necessary.
- No evidence-based guideline exists regarding best practice techniques for CLEs.

Methods

- Development of clinical practice recommendations following systematic literature review.
- Evaluate 4-month baseline data for hospital epidural failure rates and reasons for failures.

Epidural Factors Under Review

- Combined spinal/epidural (CSE) & dural puncture epidural (DPE)
- Needle bevel orientation/depth of catheter
- Epidural opioids/dosing regimen
- Epidural space identifier
- Multiport/single port catheters
- Patient positioning
- Saline pre-distention of epidural space
- Predictors of epidural failures

Practice Guidelines

Epidural Placement Variable	Evidence based recommendation	Rationale
Combined Spinal/Epidural & Dural Puncture Epidural	CSE and DPE provide a more rapid onset than traditional labor epidural; DPE is associated with less pruritis, nausea, and vomiting as compared to CSE.	Local anesthetic and narcotic injected into the subarachnoid space provides a rapid onset as compared to epidural analgesia. Side effects of these medications in the subarachnoid space include itching, nausea, and vomiting.
Epidural Needle Bevel Orientation & Depth of Catheter	Bevel should be facing cephalad in order to provide a bilateral block; epidural catheter should be threaded 3-5 cm into epidural space.	The direction of the bevel affects the spread of local anesthetic and should be facing the direction of the desired block. Epidural catheters threaded greater than 5 cm into space increase risk of intravascular cannulation and one-sided blocks. Epidural catheters threaded less than 3 cm into space have an increased risk of falling out.
Epidural Opioids/Dosing Regimen	Local anesthetics should be administered as a bolus rather than as a continuous infusion and narcotics should be co-administered.	Fentanyl administered epidurally is 3 times as potent as when it is administered intravenously. Local anesthetics delivered as a programmed intermittent bolus decreases total consumption of local anesthetic and improves analgesia as compared to a continuous infusion.
Epidural Space Identifier	Saline and air are both adequate for analgesia, however saline is a safer technique.	Air is associated with risk of pneumocephalus and venous air embolus. Contraindications to using air include epidural blood patch, and repeat epidural after a positive dural puncture due to the possible communication of air into the subarachnoid space.
Multiport/Uniport Catheters	Multiport catheters improve spread of local anesthetic and should be administered as intermittent boluses.	Multiport catheters act as single port catheters when a continuous infusion pump is utilized. Programmed intermittent boluses allow all three ports to be used, thus improving spread of local anesthetic and improving patient analgesia.
Patient Positioning	Lateral positioning decreases intravascular cannulation and migration of catheter. Taping the catheter in the lateral position decreases catheter movement.	Epidural veins are engorged during pregnancy, placing the patient at risk for intravascular cannulation. The lateral position decreases this engorgement. In obese patients the catheter has the potential to migrate up to 4cm with position changes. This is reduced when the catheter is taped with the patient in the lateral position.
Saline Pre-distension of Epidural Space	5-10ml of saline pre-distention of the epidural space greatly decreases intravascular cannulation.	Epidural vessels are engorged during pregnancy and the pre-distention of saline helps to displace vessels and aides in the threading of the catheter.

Epidural Failures in 4 Months

Factor	N (%)
Intravascular	1 (2.2%)
One-Sided	7 (15.2%)
No Analgesia	20 (43.5%)
Dural Puncture	5 (10.9%)
Failed Surgical Anesthesia	6 (13.0%)
Other	7 (15.2%)
# of punctures	
1	515
2	36
3+	8
Total Failures	46 (8.2%)

Practice Implications

Failed surgical anesthesia

- ↑ in required # of boluses indicates epidural not working well.
- If 2+ boluses required to maintain pt. comfort, epidural catheter requires replacing.

Lack of analgesia

- CSE and DPE technique can confirm proximity of epidural space.
- DPE can confirm adequacy of epidural.
- Use of ultrasound in morbidly obese patients and those with difficult anatomy may decrease failures.

One-sided blocks

- Insert the needle with the hole facing cephalad.
- Thread epidural catheters 3-5cm into space.
- Use of multi-orifice catheters may help spread of local anesthetic.

Pneumocephalus prevention

- Use saline for loss of resistance technique.
- Avoid using air for epidural blood patch.
- Avoid using air for repeat epidural after accidental dural puncture.